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Configuration and preliminary performance of the CPU for two different CO₂ target purities

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Author(s)		
Name	Organization	Email
Francesco Magli	POLIMI	francesco.magli@polimi.it
Manuele Gatti*	POLIMI	manuele.gatti@polimi.it
Maurizio Spinelli	LEAP	maurizio.spinelli@polimi.it
Matteo Romano	POLIMI	matteo.romano@polimi.it

*Lead author

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Short description

In this deliverable, two preliminary configurations of the CO₂ Purification Unit (CPU) – with a different target purity – for the full-scale integrated Calcium Looping cement plant are presented and assessed in terms of heat and material balances and electric consumption.

History of changes

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Abstract

This document provides the basis of design and a preliminary configuration with energy performance for the CO₂ Purification Unit (CPU) of the full-scale integrated Calcium Looping cement plant. Two base cases have been defined, with two different outlet CO₂ specifications: 'moderate purity' and 'high purity'.

As a consequence, two different CPU configurations, able to achieve the two different purities, have been defined. They are based on the following steps: dust abatement, first compression, dehydration, cryogenic CO₂ purification via partial condensation at low-temperatures and final compression to dense-phase conditions. The two CPUs differ for the cryogenic separation unit, which is based on (i) a double flash Vapor-Liquid separation process for the 'moderate purity' case, and on (ii) a more complex process integrating phase separation with a stripping column for the 'high purity' case.

Aspen Plus process simulations show that the 'moderate purity' case exhibits a specific electric consumption of 459 kJ/kg CO₂ and a CO₂ recovery of 97.6 %. For the 'high purity' case, the specific electric consumption rises to 499 kJ/kg CO₂, while the CO₂ recovery drops to 93.6 %.

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1. BASIS OF DESIGN

1.1 Inlet conditions: CO₂-rich stream entering the CPU

The reference full-scale integrated Calcium Looping process to be further developed in CLEANKER has been previously described and simulated by De Lena et al. (De Lena et al., 2019) according to the assumptions of the CEMCAP H2020 project (Anantharaman et al., 2015) and relying on the Best Available Technique (BAT) standard as defined in the European BREF-Document (Best Available Technique Reference) for the manufacture of cement (JRC, 2013).

In this deliverable, the “Base case” CO₂ conditions are set as follows: the cement plant size and the thermodynamic conditions of the captured CO₂ stream entering the CPU are taken from De Lena et al. (De Lena et al., 2019). The full-scale plant has a clinker production capacity of 2,817 t/d, which is a representative size for a European cement kiln.

The results of this preliminary analysis will be updated when more detailed CaLooping process simulations (Task 5.4) and first experimental pilot test results (Task 3.2) will be available in the framework of the CLEANKER project.

The configuration of the considered process is shown in Figure 1. In the integrated Calcium Looping process, the CO₂ captured in the carbonator is released as a gaseous stream from the sorbent in the calciner, which is heated via oxy-fired coal combustion. The CO₂-rich gas produced by the calciner is partly recycled to the reactor as a moderator, while the remaining fraction is sent first to heat recovery and then to the CPU, where the captured CO₂ is purified and compressed to the conditions required by the following transportation and utilization/storage steps of the CCUS chain.

Figure 1. Schematic of the cement kiln with integrated CaL process (De Lena et al., 2019).

1.1.1 Base case

Table 1 reports data for the CO₂-rich stream #29 in Figure 1, which are used in this deliverable for the preliminary sizing of the CO₂ Purification Unit (CPU).

Table 1. Conditions of the CO₂-rich stream entering the CPU (De Lena et al., 2019).

Parameter	Value
Gas mass flow rate, kg/s	37.75
Gas volumetric flow rate, Nm ³ /h	75'758
Gas composition (% vol.)	81.17% CO ₂ , 11.47% H ₂ O, 5.15% O ₂ , 1.27% Ar, 0.94% N ₂
Solids content, g/Nm ³	43.24
Temperature, °C	60
Pressure, bar(a)	0.93

1.1.2 Sensitivity analysis

The following parameters are expected to have a major influence on the composition of the CO₂-rich stream leaving the CaLooping capture plant:

- Air infiltration rates;
- Oxygen excess rates;
- Calciner fuel composition.

Therefore, a sensitivity analysis will be carried out to assess their impact on the performance of the CPU, considering reasonable combinations of the parameters listed below. The results of this analysis will be presented in deliverable 5.11, “Final report on the optimal configuration, performance and costs of the CPU for two different CO₂ target purities, including also off-design evaluation”.

Air infiltration rates

Two scenarios will be considered:

- No air infiltration. In this case, the following components are assumed to be perfectly air-tight: pre-calciner, CO₂ preheater, CO₂-rich gas ducts and coolers. This is the best-case scenario for the CPU operation, since a very low nitrogen content and, hence, minimum CO₂-dilution is expected in the stream to purify. This also represents the base case, since in the CEMCAP work by De Lena et al. (De Lena et al., 2019) all the air infiltration is located in the kiln only, without further downstream leakages.
- High air infiltration rates. This is the worst-case scenario, with an air leakage similar to the one typically reported for a traditional cement plant pre-calciner and preheater. Based on the cement industry experience, a reasonable value for this air infiltration is assumed to be 10% of the flue gas leaving the preheater tower.

Oxygen excess rates

Two cases will be considered for the oxygen excess rate:

- Preliminary full-scale Cleanker design value: the oxygen content in the gaseous stream leaving the calciner is 4% vol (wet basis). The oxygen content of the CO₂-rich stream considered in this preliminary analysis is similar but not the same value (see Table 1) because of the slightly different assumptions adopted in the CEMCAP project.
- High oxygen excess rate: the preliminary design value is 6% vol (wet basis), a value more representative of operations where complete combustion of solid and heterogeneous fuels is targeted.

Calciner fuel composition

Five different fuels, typically employed in cement plants, will be considered to provide the chemical input for the calciner:

- Coal: it is the most widely used fuel in the cement industry. It is also the fuel considered in the CEMCAP framework (De Lena et al., 2019), hence this is considered as a base case;
- CAV ('Combustibile ad Alta Viscosità'), the Highly Viscous Fuel Oil (HVFO) currently used in Vernasca: it is the design fuel for the Cleanker pilot and following experimental campaigns, and its characteristics have been provided by Buzzi Unicem;
- Natural gas: it is the fossil fuel which features the lowest CO₂ intensity per unit of primary energy supplied. It is used by the cement industry in those regions where its cost is competitive or for start-up/auxiliary operations. The average characteristics of the natural gas transported by SNAM – the Italian gas grid operator – during thermal year 2017-18 have been taken as a reference (SNAM, 2019);
- RDF ('Refuse Derived Fuel'): processed fraction of residual municipal solid waste. The European cement industry recovers a substantial amount of waste-derived fuels, which replace fossil fuels up to 80% and more in some plants (JRC, 2013). The assumed fuel composition is the average of the 30 RDF samples included in the Phyllis2 database (TNO, 2019).
- Animal meal: it is a biomass produced as a residue by slaughterhouses, and it is one of the main "pure biomass" fuels used in the cement industry today. The assumed composition and properties are the average of 12 samples of 'bone meal' and 'meat and bone meal' included in the Phyllis2 database (TNO, 2019).

Table 2 summarizes LHV, HHV and composition of the aforementioned fuels.

Table 2. Composition and energy content of the considered fuels.

Fuel	Coal	CAV (HVFO)	Natural gas	RDF	Animal meal
LHV, MJ/kg (ar*)	27.2	38.9	45.9	16.9	16.6
HHV, MJ/kg (ar*)	-	41.0	50.8	18.1	18.2
Moisture content, % wt _{ar}	0.5	0.4	-	10.2	3.8
Ash content, % wt _{ar}	16.5	1.3	-	14.6	18.4
Ultimate analysis (daf**)					
C, % wt _{daf}	83.2	88.6	73.8	55.2	52.1
H, % wt _{daf}	4.8	9.9	23.7	8.4	7.5
N, % wt _{daf}	0.6	0.5	1.6	0.9	10.9
S, % wt _{daf}	0.6	1	-	0.4	0.6
O, % wt _{daf}	10.8	0	0.9	33.7	22.8
Others (Cl, F...), %wt _{daf}	0	0	0	1.4	6.1

*As received basis

**Dry ash-free basis

1.2 Outlet specifications

The outlet specifications for the CPU depends both on the transportation system and on the final destination of the captured and purified CO₂.

The considered transportation options are:

- Pipeline. It is a known and mature market technology, with significant experience from more than 8'000 km of CO₂ pipes in the United States (2017 data) (PHMSA, 2019). There is also some experience with transport of CO₂ using offshore pipelines (around 150 km) in Snøhvit, Norway (IEA, 2013) (IEAGHG, 2014a);
- Ship. It may be economically attractive when the CO₂ has to be moved over large distances or overseas. At present, the largest ships for CO₂ transport are in the 8'500 – 10'000 m³ range (6 ships of this size are currently in operation worldwide). However, new ships are currently under design to address the specific CCS demands, hence carriers up to 30'000 – 40'000 m³ could become economically feasible. It has to be noticed that a ship-based transportation system must include, unlike a pipeline-based system, temporary storage on land and a loading facility (IPCC, 2005) (Energy Institute, 2010).

Other options, such as road and rail tankers are also technically feasible, but they are uneconomical except on a very small scale, hence they are not interesting for full-scale CCS projects in the field of cement.

The considered final CO₂ destinations are:

- Underground geological storage in deep saline formations or in depleted oil and gas reservoirs;
- Enhanced Oil Recovery (EOR) in oil reservoirs.

Other options such as ocean storage, underground storage in unminable coal beds for Enhanced Coal Bed Methane recovery (ECBM), etc., are not considered since they are less mature technologies without any significant large-scale demonstration experience or project planned.

The CO₂ quality specifications required to satisfy the above-mentioned transportation and storage/utilization options can be classified in the two following categories, summarized in Table 3.

Table 3. Outlet specifications for the CPU. Where ‘-’ is reported it means that the specification on the ‘Total’ amount applies.

			Moderate purity	High purity
Pressure		bar(a)	110	110
Temperature		°C	30	30
Composition				
CO ₂		vol% (min)	95	99.7
H ₂ O		ppmv	1	1
Non condensables	N ₂	vol%	2	-
	O ₂	ppmv	-	10
	Ar	vol%	-	-
	CH ₄	vol%	-	-
	H ₂	vol%	0.75	-
	CO	vol%	0.2	0.2
	Total	vol%	4	0.3
H ₂ S		ppmv	200	200
SO ₂		ppmv	50	50
NO _x		ppmv	50	50
Particulates		mg/Nm ³	1	1

In both cases, the water content is limited by the CPU: cryogenic heat exchangers operate close to the triple point of CO₂, hence deep dehydration is required in order to prevent the formation of ice (Berstad and Trædal, 2018).

- Moderate purity: this option considers the transport and storage system which features the least strict specifications. It is representative of a pipeline transport system operated in a hot region and storage in a deep saline formation. The ‘moderate purity’ case is based on the least strict limits set by the European standards for CO₂ pipelines (ISO 27913, 2016), under the assumption that no further limitations are given by the storage site. The content of particulates is limited as suggested by the Teesside CCS Project (AMEC, 2015);
- High purity: on the opposite side, this option considers the most severe specifications that a CO₂ transport and storage system (not deemed for food applications) can require. It is representative of a multi-modal transport system featuring both pipeline and ship transport,

located in a cold region (e.g. Northern Europe or Canada) and with final utilization of the CO₂ for EOR. Pressure and temperature are imposed by the pipeline operation, while the presence of impurities (in particular, non-condensable gases) is limited by the ship transport conditions. An additional limitation on the oxygen content is due to microbial related corrosion which may affect the pipeline in terms of corrosion, as well as injection wells, particularly for EOR (Bliss et al., 2010). The ‘high purity’ case is mainly based on the specifications for ship transport suggested by Aspelund (Maroto-Valer, 2010), while limitations on SO₂, NO_x and particulates content are kept identical to the ‘moderate purity’ option.

2. CPU DESCRIPTION

Several technologies are proposed in the literature for oxy-fuel derived CO₂ purification. However, cryogenic purification is the only option currently used in industrial applications and most recently tested in the few existing CPUs pilot plants (though not specifically design for CO₂ produced via Ca-Looping capture), hence it has been selected for the present analysis.

The phase separation principle of cryogenic CPUs is the different volatility between CO₂ and non-condensable gases (such as nitrogen, oxygen and argon). This concept can be exploited through two technical solutions:

- phase separation (often named ‘flash separation’, even though no depressurization occurs): the feed gas is partially liquefied by means of temperature reduction at constant pressure (after being previously pressurized in the gas phase). This option is suitable for the ‘moderate purity’ outlet specifications, which can be reached by a flash cascade, while avoiding more complex separation equipment such as stripping columns, cryogenic reboilers, etc.;
- stripping or distillation-based separation (properly integrated with flash separation): a stripper or a distillation column is used to further reduce the amount of contaminants in the CO₂ stream, thus allowing to reach the ‘high purity’ grade defined before.

In both cases, the thermodynamic limit, i.e. the concentration of impurities which can be achieved in CO₂ at thermodynamic equilibrium for given temperature and pressure, is set by the phase-equilibria (normally of the type Vapor-Liquid for CO₂-O₂-N₂-Ar mixtures) which occur between CO₂ and the other species of the mixture to purify.

The typical flow diagram for a CPU is summarized in Figure 2 (as conceptual blocks) and includes the following sequence of major equipment:

- a first compression step with water condensation after inter-cooling and removal by means of gravity-based separators (knock-out drums);
- a dehydration step for the further reduction of the water content down to the ppm-design specification, not attainable via inter-cooled compression only;
- the main cold box entailing cryogenic heat exchangers, phase separators and columns (where required);
- a final step of inter-cooled compression and final pumping of the purified CO₂ in the dense-phase to 110 bar.

Given the high dust content of the flue gases produced by the integrated calcium looping process, we consider an initial dedicated dust abatement step in order to protect the downstream equipment. Other purification steps such as permanganate towers for NO_x and SO_x control or guard beds for other minor impurities have not been considered in this work, but may be included upstream of the CPU depending on the specific amounts of contaminants to be removed.

Figure 2. Block flow diagram of a generic cryogenic purification process applicable to the flue gases produced by the integrated Calcium Looping process.

The Process Flow Diagram configuration for the two target purities, together with a description of the single components design and performance assumptions are provided in the following sections.

Alternative CO₂ purification technologies, based on different separation principles, may be integrated with the cryogenic CPU to recover the CO₂ lost in the non-condensable gas stream and increase the total amount of CO₂ recovered. The most interesting ones are: adsorption on solid materials (P/TSA, Pressure/Temperature Swing Adsorption) (Shah et al., 2011), membrane separation (White et al., 2006), or recycle to the carbonator reactor (De Lena et al., 2017). However, at this preliminary stage of the CPU design, it is assumed that none of those techniques are integrated in the CPU.

2.1 CPU configuration

2.1.1 Moderate purity

The CPU configuration selected for the ‘moderate purity’ target is shown in Figure 3. The process configuration replicates the one proposed by IEAGHG (IEAGHG, 2011) for the purification of flue gases produced by an oxy-fuel boiler, with the addition of an initial dust abatement step ahead of the low pressure compression. This configuration exploits a double flash separation process for the main cryogenic unit. The compression system design is based on the ‘Oxy-fuel – Optimized inter-cooling as specified’ configuration presented by AMEC-Foster-Wheeler (IEAGHG, 2011), since the nominal flow-rates and impurities type and final concentrations are in line with the specifications set for the ‘moderate purity’ case of this analysis.

In this scheme, no expanders are placed on the vapor branch leaving the phase separator, because according to the preliminary analysis they would have a small size even in the full-scale plant, since they could generate a few hundred kilowatts of electricity and a similar amount of low temperature cooling duty, hence without dramatically affecting the energy performance of the CPU. However, the final decision on the convenience of cryogenic expanders in the CPU depends on the techno-economic optimization which be carried out in D5.11.

Figure 3. 'Moderate purity' CPU process configuration.

2.1.2 High purity

The CPU configuration selected for the 'high purity' target is shown in Figure 4. It is based on a process configuration patented by Air Products (White and Allam, 2008), in the version presented by Strube and Manfrida (Strube and Manfrida, 2011), again with the addition of an initial dust abatement unit. In this configuration, the main cold box features a flash separator and a stripping column with reboiler, and the compression system is, again, based on the 'Oxy-fuel – Optimized inter-cooling as specified' scheme presented by IEAGHG (IEAGHG, 2011).

Figure 4. 'High purity' CPU process configuration.

2.2 Process modelling assumptions

CPUs have been simulated with the flowsheeting software Aspen Plus v10 in order to assess their heat and mass balances. On the other hand, the behavior of the dust abatement and dehydration steps have not been simulated in detail, because they are usually included as separate packages in the CPU and, moreover, they have a minor impact on the overall energy consumption of the CPU, compared to compressors. Hence, for these units we assumed specific consumption values from the literature.

The main modeling assumptions for the simulations are:

- Heat and material balances are calculated for steady-state design conditions.
- Peng-Robinson equation of state with Van der Waals mixing rules has been adopted for the evaluation of the properties of all the streams involved in the simulations. Aspen Plus v10 default parameters have been kept for all the model parameters, except for the binary parameter k_{ij} for CO₂-O₂ and CO₂-Ar binary mixtures: the assumed values are reported in Table 4 (Li and Yan, 2009).

Table 4. Binary parameter k_{ij} assumed for CO₂-O₂ and CO₂-Ar mixtures (Li and Yan, 2009).

Mixture	k_{ij}
CO ₂ -O ₂	0.114
CO ₂ -Ar	0.163

- The stripping column of the ‘high purity’ case has been simulated as an equilibrium Rad-Frac component. For this component, a rate-based modeling approach would help in carrying out a more rigorous column design, while understanding the actual performances resulting from deviations from the thermodynamic equilibrium and the presence of heat and mass transfer resistances (in particular, for very high purity requirements understand the actual column packed height or the number of bubble cap trays required, in case a more traditional tray column is preferred). However, the calibration of a rate-based model requires experimental data from pilot-plant (or at least bench scale) columns, which are not available from the CLEANKER project (where the CPU is not meant to be built) and are scarce in the literature for CO₂ strippers; therefore, in this preliminary deliverable the mixtures leaving the column are assumed to be at the thermodynamic equilibrium and neither rate-based modelling, nor detailed thermo-hydraulic design of the column is carried out. Moreover, this approach has been widely used in the literature for similar case studies (Strube and Manfrida, 2011) (Wagener and Rochelle, 2010).
- Flash drums have been modeled as adiabatic separators at the equilibrium, without pressure drops and no losses for liquid entrainment in the vapor phase.
- Compressors have been modeled as adiabatic machine with specified polytropic efficiency, using ASME method.

2.3 Dust abatement

As far as the dust content is concerned, the CO₂-rich stream leaving the calciner in the integrated CaL process is similar to a traditional cement kiln gas stream, before dust abatement. Two main technologies are currently adopted in the cement sector: electrostatic filters (ESP) and bag filters. Both solutions are able to reduce the dust content below 10 mg/Sm³ (dry state, 10% O₂) with similar electricity consumption, in the 1.5 – 2 kWh/t_{clinker} range (Anantharaman et al., 2015). IEAGHG considers flue gases from coal-fired power plants with a particulate matter concentration around 10-20 mg/Nm³ and does not report problems for compression, liquefaction and transportation (IEAGHG, 2016): hence, it is assumed that a typical dust abatement device is sufficient to protect the downstream equipment.

Since maintenance costs are reported to be in favour of bag filters (Anantharaman et al., 2015) and due to the higher separation efficiency, we consider to adopt this technology, under the assumptions summarized in Table 5. In particular, the specific electric consumption per metric ton of dust removed corresponds to a consumption of 1.5 kWh/t_{dust removed}.

Table 5. Assumptions for the dust abatement system.

Parameter	Unit of measure	Value
Technology	-	Bag filter
Pressure drop	mbar	12
Specific electric consumption	kWh/t _{dust removed}	18.9

2.4 First compression

The compression system is based on the same design presented by Foster Wheeler in the IEAGHG report for the ‘Oxy-fuel – Optimized inter-cooling as specified’ scheme: compressors are of the centrifugal type, with variable speed drivers to optimize the efficiency of each compression step. As a matter of fact, this scheme operates with a similar input stream and the size of the single compression train (117’060 Nm³/h for the first compression step) is of the same order of magnitude of the one needed for the CLEANKER full-scale application (69’490 Nm³/h) (IEAGHG, 2011). Hence, the compression ratios (or stage load) as well as polytropic efficiencies are derived by the aforementioned report.

The first compression block is composed of:

- A first blower which increases the pressure of the de-dusted flue gases up to a constant value, in order to allow the compressors downstream to operate as close as possible to design conditions.
- Compressor 1, which includes 4 intercooled centrifugal compressor groups of 2 stages each, all mounted on the same shaft. The outlet pressure is 15 bar.
- Compressor 2, composed of a 2-stages intercooled compressor. It works with a compressor ratio slightly higher than 2, but with a compression outlet temperature always lower than 100 °C.

The gaseous stream recycled from the dehydration unit, comprising nearly 10% of the overall CO₂ processed, is recycled back to compressor 2, to ensure full dehydration without CO₂ losses in the dryer. The configuration of the first compression step with details on the number of stages is shown in Figure 5, while the main assumptions for its simulation are reported in Table 6.

Table 6. Assumptions for the first compression step. The names are referred to Figure 5.

Parameter	Unit of measure	Value
BLOWER – Outlet pressure	bar(a)	1.013
BLOWER – Polytropic efficiency	%	87
Compressor 1		
COMP 1.1 – Compression ratio	-	2
COMP 1.1 – Polytropic efficiency	%	87
COMP 1.2 – Compression ratio	-	2
COMP 1.2 – Polytropic efficiency	%	88
COMP 1.3 – Compression ratio	-	2
COMP 1.3 – Polytropic efficiency	%	88
COMP 1.4 – Compression ratio	-	2
COMP 1.4 – Polytropic efficiency	%	86
Compressor 2		
COMP 2 – Outlet pressure	bar(a)	31
COMP 2 – Polytropic efficiency	%	85
Pressure drop in the intercoolers	%	2
Intercoolers outlet temperature	°C	28
Electric consumption associated to intercoolers	kW _{el} /kW _{th rejected}	0.01
Electro-mechanical efficiency of compressors	%	95

Figure 5. Schematic of the first compression step.

2.5 Dehydration

Two main water removal options are typically considered for the dehydration of CO₂-rich streams: the TEG (triethylene glycol) process and solid bed adsorption.

We consider to adopt solid bed adsorption units because of two main advantages: a life-cycle cost lower than TEG units and a higher flexibility in terms of target moisture attainable in the outlet gas (down to 1 ppm vs 30 ppm). Moreover, the capital cost of solid bed adsorption units is reported to be similar for target moistures of 550 ppmv, 50 ppmv and < 10 ppmv, with differences in the operating costs. On the other hand, a fraction of the treated gas has to be recycled for bed regeneration purposes. The regeneration is carried out by means of a temperature swing in the dehydration beds. The necessary heat is provided by steam extracted from the steam turbine: hence, the electricity consumption for regeneration represents this loss of power production. The sorbent media life is typically around 3 years. (IEAGHG, 2014b) (IEAGHG, 2011). The modeling assumptions for this unit are reported in Table 7.

Table 7. Assumptions for the dehydration system.

Parameter	Unit of measure	Value
Technology	-	Solid bed adsorption
Recycle rate	kg _{recycle} /kg _{inlet}	0.1
Pressure drop	bar	1
Operating pressure	bar(a)	30
Electricity consumption	kWh _{el} /kgH ₂ O removed	2.29

2.6 Cryogenic separation unit

In the followings, the configuration of the cold box is presented for the two target purities. The main difference between the process configurations is the presence of a stripping column in the ‘high purity’ case, which allows to meet the stricter outlet specifications. However, it must be noticed that a higher purity of the outlet CO₂ stream inherently reflects on a lower CO₂ recovery (i.e. the ratio between the amount of CO₂ leaving the unit as pure and the total amount of CO₂ entering the unit itself) and therefore the energy consumption for CO₂ capture increases.

2.6.1 Moderate purity

The configuration of the cold box for the ‘moderate purity’ case is shown in Figure 6. It is based on the process configuration presented by Foster Wheeler in the IEAGHG report for the ‘Oxy-fuel – Optimized inter-cooling as specified’ case (IEAGHG, 2011). It involves two cryogenic multi-flow heat exchangers (plate-fin type, commonly employed in air separation units), two phase separation drums and two valves to provide auto-refrigeration by means of the purified CO₂ throttling at suitable pressure levels. The vapor stream released by the second flash separator (SEP 2) is heated while providing a small fraction of the cooling duty in the cryogenic heat exchangers HX 1 and HX 2, and

a final heater (HX 3) is included to attain close-to atmospheric temperatures after the last expansion valve (VAL 3). In this preliminary analysis a valve (VAL 3) has been selected instead of an expander because of the small size of the component and a techno-economic analysis (D5.11) should clarify whether it is convenient or not. Separation pressures values are kept equal to the values reported in IEAGHG (IEAGHG, 2011). Liquid throttling pressures have been adjusted to achieve the targeted separation pressure while operating an auto-refrigerated cryogenic separation unit with minimum process temperatures equal or higher than $-53\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ (with a margin higher than $3\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ against the triple point of pure CO_2). All the modeling assumptions for this unit are reported in Table 8.

Figure 6. Schematic of the cryogenic separation unit for the ‘moderate purity’ target.

Table 8. Assumptions for the cryogenic separation unit, ‘moderate purity’ target.

Parameter	Unit of measure	Value
Pressure drop in the heat exchangers	% of inlet pressure	2
Minimum temperature difference in the heat exchangers	K	3
Minimum gas/liquid temperature	$^{\circ}\text{C}$	-53
VAL 1 outlet pressure	bar(a)	18.9
VAL 2 outlet pressure	bar(a)	9.7
VAL 3 outlet pressure	bar(a)	1.1
HX 3 outlet temperature	$^{\circ}\text{C}$	40

2.6.2 High purity

The configuration of the cold box for the ‘high purity’ CO₂ target is shown in Figure 7. It is based on a process concept patented by Air Products (White and Allam, 2008), in the version presented by Strube and Manfrida (Strube and Manfrida, 2011). It adopts a single main cryogenic heat exchanger (HX 1), a phase separation step (SEP) followed by a stripping column (STRIPPER) where the liquid of the separator is first flashed (VAL 1) and then purified with the aid of a reboiler in the column. The purified CO₂ stream is throttled and vaporized to generate the auto-refrigeration duty for the cryogenic heat exchanger, and then sent to the final compression step as two streams at different pressures. The vapor stream leaving the top of the stripper is heated in the main heat exchanger (HX 1) and is eventually recycled to the inlet of the cryogenic separation unit: an intercooled recompression step is needed (COMP + HX 3). For the same reasons of the ‘moderate purity’ case, a valve (VAL 4) is selected in place of an expander to bring the vapor stream (containing impurities and the unrecovered CO₂) to the atmospheric pressure. All the modeling assumptions for this scheme are reported in

Table 9.

Figure 7. Schematic of the cryogenic separation unit for the ‘high purity’ target.

Table 9. Assumptions for the cryogenic separation unit, ‘high purity’ target.

Parameter	Unit of measure	Value
Pressure drop in the heat exchangers	%	2
Minimum temperature difference in the heat exchangers	K	3
Minimum gas temperature	°C	-53
SEP pressure	bar(a)	28
SEP temperature	°C	-40
VAL 1 outlet pressure	bar(a)	17
VAL 2 outlet pressure	bar(a)	12
VAL 3 outlet pressure	bar(a)	8.5
HX 2 outlet temperature	°C	40
COMP polytropic efficiency	%	84
COMP outlet pressure	bar(a)	30
STRIPPER operating pressure	bar(a)	17
Pressure drop in STRIPPER	bar(a)	0.1
Column type	-	Equilibrium column with 10 ideal stages
Reboiler temperature	°C	-24
HX 3 outlet temperature	°C	28
Electric consumption associated to intercoolers	kW _{el} /kW _{th rejected}	0.01

2.7 Final compression

The final compression step has been simulated assuming a similar configuration for the two target purities. Both cryogenic separation units produce two CO₂ streams at different pressures, hence two steps are needed:

- Compressor 3 compresses the low-p stream to the same pressure of the high-p one. This step is done by a single-stage intercooled centrifugal compressor (COMP 3). Then, the compressed gas is mixed with the high-pressure CO₂ stream leaving the cryogenic separation unit.
- Compressor 4 operates with the entire CO₂ flow in order to reach the final pressure for transportation. In the ‘moderate purity’ case, this step is carried out by two intercooled centrifugal compressors. In the ‘high purity’ case, a third intercooler is added in order to limit the outlet temperature below 100°C, a technological standard reported by IEAGHG (IEAGHG, 2011).

All the machines are assumed to be mounted on the same shaft. The common assumptions for the simulation of the final compression step of both cases are reported in Table 10.

Table 10. Common assumptions for the final compression.

Parameter	Unit of measure	Value
Pressure drop in the intercoolers	%	2
Intercoolers outlet temperature	°C	28
Electric consumption associated to intercoolers	kW _{el} /kW _{th rejected}	0.01
Electro-mechanical efficiency of compressors	%	95

2.7.1 Moderate purity

Figure 8 shows the process flow diagram of the final compression step for the ‘moderate purity’ target, while Table 11 reports the specific simulation assumptions.

Figure 8. Schematic of the final compression – ‘Moderate purity’.

Table 11. Assumptions for the final compression – ‘Moderate purity’.

Parameter	Unit of measure	Value
Compressor 3		
COMP 3 – Compression ratio	-	2
COMP 3 – Polytropic efficiency	%	84
Compressor 4		
COMP 4.1 – Compression ratio	-	2.4
COMP 4.1 – Polytropic efficiency	%	84.6
COMP 4.2 – Outlet pressure	bar(a)	112
COMP 4.2 – Polytropic efficiency	%	84

2.7.2 High purity

Figure 9 shows the process flow diagram of the final compression step for the ‘high purity’ target, while Table 12 reports the specific simulation assumptions.

Figure 9. Schematic of the final compression – ‘High purity’.

Table 12. Assumptions for the final compression – ‘High purity’.

Parameter	Unit of measure	Value
Compressor 3		
COMP 3 – Compression ratio	-	1.4
COMP 3 – Polytropic efficiency	%	84
Compressor 4		
COMP 4.1 – Compression ratio	-	2.7
COMP 4.1 – Polytropic efficiency	%	84.6
COMP 4.2 – Outlet pressure	-	2
COMP 4.2 – Polytropic efficiency	%	84
COMP 4.2 – Outlet pressure	bar(a)	112
COMP 4.2 – Polytropic efficiency	%	84

3. RESULTS

The main results of the simulations are reported in Table 13. The specific electric consumption of the ‘high purity’ case is around 10 % higher than the ‘moderate purity’ case. Moreover, stricter limitations on the impurities reflect on a lower recovery of CO₂, which drops from 97.6 % to 93.6 %.

Table 14 highlights the breakdown of the electric consumptions into the steps described in the previous chapter. The breakdown of the specific electric consumptions is also reported in a graphical form in Figure 10. The absolute consumption is equal for the 2 target purities until the end of the first compression step, since the same stream is treated by the same machinery: however, the lower recovery associated to the ‘high purity’ case penalizes the specific consumption for these steps too. The ‘high purity’ case features a slightly more energy intensive dehydration system per unit of delivered purified CO₂, but the main source of the global difference in the consumption is due to the final compression step, which operates starting from the lower pressures given by the cryogenic unit that has to achieve the higher purity. A small additional consumption is also related to the recompression of the internal recycle of the cryogenic unit, which is present in the ‘high purity’ option only.

Table 13. Main results for the two target purities.

Parameter	Unit of measure	Moderate purity	High purity
CO ₂ at CPU inlet (to be purified)	kg/s	33.54	33.54
Pure CO ₂ mass flow rate	kg/s	32.74	31.38
	t/h	117.9	113.0
CO ₂ recovery	%	97.61	93.57
Electric consumption	kW	15'027	15'669
Specific electric consumption	kJ/kgCO ₂ purified	459.0	499.3

Table 14. Breakdown of electric consumption and specific electric consumption for the 2 target purities.

	Moderate purity		High purity	
	Electric consumption, kW	Specific electric consumption, kJ/kgCO ₂ purified	Electric consumption, kW	Specific electric consumption, kJ/kgCO ₂ purified
Dust removal	62	1.9	62	2.0
First compression	10'374	316.9	10'374	330.6
Dehydration	366	11.2	366	11.7
Cryogenic separation (recycle compression)	0	0	175	5.6
Final compression	4'225	129.1	4'691	149.5
Total	15'026	459.0	15'669	499.3

Figure 10. Breakdown of specific electric consumption for the two target purities.

The properties of the main streams of the ‘moderate purity’ and ‘high purity’ cases are reported in Table 15 and Table 16. The streams names refer to Figure 11 and Figure 12, respectively. Even though the stripping column is deemed to be capable to achieve very high CO₂ purity, to advance the technology readiness level of the full CaLooping-based CCS chain, the actual design, sizing, set-up, performance and effectiveness of the column should be demonstrated by building and testing a CPU scheme such as the one of Figure 7 (or at least reproducing the stripping column) in a relevant industrial environment.

Figure 11. ‘Moderate purity’ CPU process configuration with streams ID.

Table 15. Properties of the main streams of the ‘Moderate purity’ CPU shown in Figure 11.

#	m kg/s	n mol/s	T °C	p bara	Composition, %mol				
					CO ₂	H ₂ O	O ₂	Ar	N ₂
1	37.75	938.9	60	0.9	81.17	11.47	5.15	1.27	0.94
2	36.35	861.2	37	1.0	88.49	3.50	5.61	1.38	1.02
3	39.83	926.0	28	14.9	91.44	0.28	5.80	1.43	1.05
4	39.81	924.8	28	31.0	91.56	0.15	5.81	1.43	1.06
5	1.92	106.4	28	0.9	0.00	100	0.00	0.00	0.00
6	0.02	1.1	27	30.0	0.00	100	0.00	0.00	0.00
7	35.81	831.3	27	30.0	91.70	0.00	5.81	1.43	1.06
8	2.28	63.0	28	1.1	28.92	0.00	48.47	12.92	9.69
9	31.38	718.7	15	18.6	96.95	0.00	2.24	0.47	0.34
10	2.15	49.5	10	9.3	95.38	0.00	3.43	0.69	0.50
11	33.53	768.2	28	110.0	96.85	0.00	2.31	0.49	0.35
12	4.43	112.6	-28	29.4	58.16	0.00	28.66	7.54	5.65
13	2.28	63.0	-50	28.8	28.92	0.00	48.47	12.92	9.69

Figure 12. ‘High purity’ CPU process configuration with stream names.

Table 16. Properties of the main streams of the ‘High purity’ CPU shown in Figure 12.

#	m kg/s	n mol/s	T °C	p bara	Composition, %mol				
					CO ₂	H ₂ O	O ₂	Ar	N ₂
1	37.75	938.9	60	0.9	81.17	11.47	5.15	1.27	0.94
2	36.35	861.2	37	1.0	88.49	3.50	5.61	1.38	1.02
3	39.83	926.0	28	14.9	91.44	0.28	5.80	1.43	1.05
4	39.81	924.8	28	31.0	91.56	0.15	5.81	1.43	1.06
5	1.92	106.4	28	0.9	0.00	100	0.00	0.00	0.00
6	0.02	1.2	28	0.9	0.00	100	0.00	0.00	0.00
7	35.81	831.1	27	30.0	91.70	0.00	5.81	1.43	1.06
8	4.42	118.0	3	1.1	41.54	0.00	40.94	10.07	7.44
9	28.24	641.8	11	11.6	99.99	1 ppm	10 ppm	traces	traces
10	3.14	71.3	11	8.5	99.99	1 ppm	10 ppm	traces	traces
11	31.38	713.1	28	110.0	99.99	1 ppm	10 ppm	traces	traces
12	40.58	947.8	-17	29.4	77.32	0.00	16.18	3.75	2.75
13	40.58	947.8	-21	28.8	71.50	0.00	20.28	4.74	3.48
14	36.16	829.8	-37	17.0	96.14	0.00	2.91	0.56	0.39
15	4.78	116.7	-35	16.9	72.59	0.00	20.66	3.95	2.80
16	4.78	116.7	-30	16.5	72.59	0.00	20.66	3.95	2.80

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